

A FRAMEWORK FOR PRIVACY PRESERVATION WITH ACTIVE VOICE AUTHENTICATION AND DEVICE CONTROL USING MACHINE LEARNING

¹Shreya, ²Raghav Goel, ³Priyanshi Katariya, ⁴Harshit Kamboj, ⁵Nirbhay Kashyap

¹Student, Amity University Sector-125, Noida-201301, Noida, India, shreyaofficial26@gmail.com

²Student, Amity University Sector-125, Noida-201301, Noida, India, raghavgoel27@gmail.com

³Student, Amity University Sector-125, Noida-201301, Noida, India, k.priyanshikatariya@gmail.com

⁴Student, Amity University Sector-125, Noida-201301, Noida, India, harshitkkamboj@gmail.com

⁵Assistant Professor (Grade – II), Amity University Sector-125, Noida-201301, Noida, India, nkashyap@amity.edu

ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to propose a method for safeguarding user privacy in a designated environment by utilizing speech patterns to differentiate genuine users from fraudulent or cloned speech users, or to grant access to specific features. Our approach entails training a model that accurately distinguishes between male, female, male-tempered voice, and female-tempered voice recordings. To achieve this, we systematically classify a dataset of seven-hundred and fifty audio recordings where multiple speakers, including the authors of this paper, articulate the same word for an identical duration. The key factor that distinguishes each speaker is their unique speech delivery pattern, frequency, and pitch. The distinct characteristics of AI-generated voices are critical in identifying their origin. The findings of this study will contribute significantly to creating a secure environment for users to interact in.

Keywords-- voice authentication, voice assistant, device control, and machine learning, enhanced cat swarm optimization(ecso)

I. INTRODUCTION

The scope of the designated environment in this study encompasses any platform that facilitates communication and enables voice-controlled tasks such as voice assistants and device control [1][2]. In the virtual realm, identifying genuine individuals is a complex undertaking; however, behavioural analysis can assist in this regard. Conducting behavioural analysis entails analysing substantial amounts of data. In this paper, we propose using speech patterns as a means of conducting behavioural analysis. To this end, we developed an in-house dataset and categorized the data as target and non-target variables.

Objective

The objective of this study is to create and implement an architecture that employs efficient and well-organized detection techniques on a dataset that includes both genuine and cloned audio recordings, with contributions from team members. After successful authentication, two additional features, namely voice assistant and device control, will be provided.

Our aim is to propose a system that can detect fake or cloned voices more effectively in the defined environment during conversations and provide additional features after authentication. This system will leverage the strengths of machine learning algorithms to improve the accuracy and efficiency of voice authentication and provide users with a more secure and robust voice-controlled system. Through this project, we hope to make significant strides towards optimizing the detection of fake voices and promoting a safer and more reliable voice-controlled environment for users.

Features

This study is focused on the development of a system that can accurately distinguish between male and female voices in a defined environment [3][4][5]. Two classifiers will be implemented to improve the accuracy of the system, and the results will be compared using a confusion matrix.

In addition to voice authentication, this project aims to develop a demonstrable system that incorporates features such as voice assistant and device control, which will be accessible after successful authentication. By

leveraging the latest advancements in machine learning and artificial intelligence, and hope to create a secure and efficient system that offers users a seamless and intuitive voice-controlled experience.

The primary goal of this study is to provide a reliable and effective means of detecting fake or cloned voices in the defined environment and to enhance the user experience through the integration of additional features. Through this project, we aim to contribute to the development of more advanced and sophisticated voice-controlled systems that can meet the needs and expectations of users in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

The final system will consist of a demonstrable implementation of classifiers trained on the dataset, a working voice assistant, and device control. The system's accuracy will be evaluated using confusion matrices to identify the most effective classifier for detecting fake or cloned voices in the defined environment.

To ensure ease of deployment and accessibility, the system will be implemented using Flask, a popular web development framework in Python. By leveraging Flask, we aim to create a user-friendly and intuitive system that can be easily deployed and accessed by users.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Identity plays a crucial role in any platform, and the defined environment is no exception. In this section, we aim to review recent advancements in speech recognition. Speech recognition has seen significant progress in recent years, with the advent of machine learning and deep learning algorithms. These algorithms have proven to be highly effective in recognizing speech patterns, enabling us to classify and identify various characteristics of a person's speech, including gender, age, and even emotional state [3].

One of the most significant advancements in speech recognition has been the development of neural network-based models, which have significantly improved accuracy and efficiency in speech recognition tasks. These models rely on large datasets for training, which enables them to learn and recognize various speech patterns with high accuracy.

Another area of recent advancement in speech recognition is the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which are particularly effective in speech recognition tasks that involve the analysis of spectrograms and other types of frequency data.

Overall, these advancements in speech recognition have enabled us to better analyze and understand the behavioral patterns of users in the defined environment, and thereby improve the security and authenticity of the platform.

Existing Methods

To address the issue of voice spoofing, researchers proposed a model for synthetic speech detection that used a fused feature vector of MFCC, GTCC, Spectral Flux, and Spectral Centroid for audio signal representation [6]. Their proposed model captured speech features, which were then used to differentiate between genuine and spoofed speech.

A hybrid model was also proposed which consists of two stages to differentiate between genuine and spoofed speech [7]. ResSEnet was used to distinguish between genuine and spoofed speech. This model was capable of handling both speech and non-speech audio using loh-mel features. The creators of this model evaluated their experiment on the Logical Access dataset ASVspoof 2019.

Approaches towards the Upgrade

To develop more advanced speech recognition systems, it is important to identify the right area for the technology. Depending on the specific use case, platforms may need different speech recognition systems such as hate speech recognition or cloning detection. Choosing the correct technical approach is the next step, which may involve using machine learning (ML), deep neural networks (DNN), acoustic modeling, hidden Markov model (HMM), or leveraging third-party APIs such as speech-to-text, automatic speech recognition (ASR), and speech recognizers in combination.

By leveraging the appropriate technical approach, the foundation for developing powerful speech recognition tools can be laid. This can lead to more optimized and effective detection of fake or unreal voices in a conversation, as well as provide additional features after authentication. Identifying the most appropriate approach and building upon it with robust training and testing methodologies can help improve the overall performance of speech recognition systems.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Dataset

The present study involves the creation of a unique dataset consisting of audio recordings for the purpose of developing a system capable of detecting cloned voices. The dataset was constructed in-house with the assistance of team members. Ten commonly used words, including "air," "water," "computer," and "soil," were chosen as the basis for the dataset. Each word was pronounced by multiple speakers in various ways, resulting in a diverse set of recordings. Specifically, each speaker produced five unique variants of a single word, including variations in speed, tone, and emotion.

The resulting dataset comprises 150 audio files for male and another 150 files for female voices. All the audio files were initially in MP3 format but were converted to WAV format using online tools to facilitate further analysis. The dataset was designed to highlight the unique speech characteristics of each speaker, including their delivery style, pitch, frequency, and number of pauses.

To generate cloned voices for experimentation, two target voices (Target 1 and Target 2) were selected - one male and one female. Using online voice-changing software, two additional voices (Target 3 and Target 4) were created based on the selected targets. These cloned voices were then used as inputs for developing and testing the proposed system for detecting cloned voices.

This resulted in 750 audio files in total, 150 for each male, female, male-tempered, female-tempered and the target.

Figure 1: Dataset audio folder

Figure 2: Audio file.

Data Pre-processing and Exploratory Data Analysis

To prepare the data for our speech recognition model, we initially stored the recorded audio files from Google Drive and accessed them through Google Colaboratory. Google Colaboratory is an online platform designed to facilitate the development and execution of machine learning and deep learning models. The audio files were labelled with names in the format "{person number} . {recording number} ". To pre-process the data, we created an array of the paths of all the recordings and used the split function to extract the person numbers, which were then combined horizontally with the paths to create a data frame consisting of two columns: person number and path.

To analyse the wave plots and spectrograms of the audio files, we developed two functions that utilized the Librosa module in Python. Spectrograms, which are graphical representations of the frequency spectrum of a signal as it changes over time, were generated by the `melspectrogram()` function [6][9]. Performed Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) on the dataset using these functions to investigate how the wave plots of different individuals speaking the same phrases varied. Our EDA results clearly demonstrated that voices differ significantly in the way speaker speak, regardless of other factors such as age and gender.

MFCC, ZCR, RMSV, `chroma_stft` is used to obtain the features of the audio that can be used in training the model as well as testing it [6-13]. In addition to that different audio augmentation techniques used to increase dataset size and diversity. To create spectrograms for the audio files, and developed a function called `get_sample()`. This function takes three inputs: the path of the audio file, the corresponding person number, and the path of the output folder where the spectrogram should be saved. To obtain the wave data and sampling rate of the audio, used the `librosa.load()` function, which takes the path of the audio file as an input. The resulting wave data, an array of audio-time series, was then fed into the `melspectrogram()` function to generate the spectrogram [14][15]. Used all the spectrograms generated by this process to construct a dataset consisting of two columns: the path of the spectrogram file and the person to whom the spectrogram belongs. This dataset was shuffled and divided into training and validation sets at a 5:3 ratio.

After getting most of the features using the `mfcc`, `zcr`, `chroma_stft`, `melspectrogram`, and `rmsv`, there is large number of features which are not much useful and can be avoided and so at this point comes the feature selection part, which is basically selecting most useful features from the given set of features.

Implemented the ECSO (Enhanced Cat Swarm Optimization) on the training set [16][17]. The algorithm for the ECSO is shown below:

1. Start with a starting population of feature subsets: The first step is to create a starting population of feature subsets, where each subset contains a different combination of features that are extracted from the speech signal. The count of features in each subset can vary, but typically it is a compact subset of the larger set of features.
2. Evaluate the fitness of each feature subset using a speech recognition system. The system takes the chosen feature subset as input and outputs the predicted label for the speech signal.
3. Apply the contrasting preservation mechanism to maintain a high level of diversity in the population: The contrasting preservation mechanism in ECSO helps to maintain a high level of diversity in the population of feature subsets. This ensures that the algorithm explores a wide range of feature subsets and avoids getting stuck in local optima.

Finally, evaluated the prepared dataset using five different supervised learning models. The Flow of Data Preprocessing is shown in the below diagram Figure 3. For the Web Application part as well, used flow chart shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Model Pipeline.

The Complete Model Pipeline is explained through the below algorithm.

1. Collecting the dataset, set the path to the dataset and create a list of all the subdirectories in the dataset.
2. Create empty lists to store the emotion and path of each audio file in the dataset.
3. Use a for loop to extract the emotion and path of each audio file and store them in their respective lists.
4. Create data frames for the emotion and path of each file and concatenate them to create one data frame.
5. Define a function to add noise to an audio signal, to stretch the time domain of an audio signal, to shift the time domain of an audio signal, to pitch shift an audio signal, to extract features from an audio signal such as Zero Crossing Rate, Chroma_stft, MFCC, RMS, and MelSpectrogram, to get the features of an audio signal with augmentation to increase the diversity and size of the dataset.
6. Split the dataset.
 - 6.a Training Set and Validation Set.
 - 6.b Test Set.
7. Used ECSO (Enhanced Cat Swarm Optimization) for feature selection on training set.
8. Train the five different models using the training data and validation data.
9. Predict the labels of the test data and generate a classification report and confusion matrix to evaluate the model's performance.

Figure 4: Flow chart of the web application

The algorithm for the whole flow chart of the web application is shown below.

1. Check whether the voice is authenticated.
 - 1.a If not authenticated, prompt the user to authenticate with their voice.
 - 1.b If authentication is successful, proceed to the next step.
2. Display the main menu with two options: "Voice Assistant" and "Device Control".
3. If the user selects "Voice Assistant":
 - 3.a Depending on the voice command the features like searching online, video playing, jokes, facts and news can be used.
4. If the user selects "Device Control":
 - 4.a Depending on the voice commands the device will get activated.
5. User can use both the options again after using it any number of time until user is authenticated successfully.

Training and Testing the Data, Calculating the Accuracy and implementing the web application part.

The following steps are used to test the data.

1. Fitting the five different model with trained dataset.
2. Testing it over the test set.
3. Taking random state as 200, max iteration as 1000, Neighbors' as 15 [18-21].

Then drawing the confusion matrix for each model.

For web applications, flask is used and for voice assistant used pyaudio for collecting audio of the user and for device control used Arduino [22]. Arduino microcontrollers are versatile and inexpensive boards that can be programmed to interact with a variety of sensors and actuators [23-24]. One of the most popular uses for Arduino boards is to control servo motors, which are devices that can rotate to a specific angle in response to a signal. By connecting a servo motor to an Arduino board and creating a system that responds to voice commands.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The presented research trained a model on a dataset of 750 audio files and obtained results from various models. The best score of 95.556% was achieved by the Random Forest algorithm. To summarize the model's performance, classification reports were generated, which revealed promising and sustainable results. The f1-

score was found to be 0.99, indicating high accuracy for the dataset consisting of 750 audios, including cloned and augmented audios. Therefore, the model is deemed suitable for large-scale deployment, with an accuracy of 96.00%.

Figure 5: Accuracy comparison graph of ML algorithms used.

Figure 6: Random Forest Confusion Matrix

```
['Telephonic Female', 'Telephonic Female']
Random Forest Class report:
precision  recall  f1-score  support
Female    1.00    0.97    0.99     74
Male      0.89    0.99    0.94     96
Telephonic Female  0.98    0.99    0.99    101
Telephonic Male  0.97    0.87    0.92     89

accuracy          0.96    360
macro avg         0.96    0.95    0.96    360
weighted avg      0.96    0.96    0.96    360
```

Figure 7: Classification Report of Test Data

Therefore, deployed this model as a web application. HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and Bootstrap were used to design the front-end while Flask, a popular framework in Python, was used for back-end [25-30].

Figure 8: Home page of Web Application

Figure 9: Post-successful-authentication page

Upon successful voice authentication, the system activates two features, namely Voice Assistant and Device Controller. Clicking on “Go to Voice Assistant” activates the voice assistant for the user. The user can request it for today’s news headlines, information related to any topic, the weather, to play YouTube videos, jokes, or facts through their voice. Based on the user's input, the voice assistant is designed to execute the respective task.

Clicking on “Go to Device Controller” enables the user to command connected devices through their voice. Devices like Arduino microcontrollers and servo motors can be easily controlled through voice commands.

When the user says commands such as “rotate” or “turn left”, the voice gets translated to text first and then into signals that can be understood by the microcontroller which in turn conveys it to the servo motor connected.

V. CONCLUSION

In terms of future work, our project aims to expand its capabilities by incorporating the identification of emotions in the speaker's voice, as has been explored in previous research [31]. Additionally, to develop a user-friendly interface for smartphone users [32]. The present model lacks the ability to recognize emotions conveyed through voice [33][34]. While it works well for tempered voice and telephonic voice, its performance on other cloned voices has not been evaluated. Furthermore, the model's feature extraction process is not comprehensive and may be enhanced in the future, potentially altering its results. Additionally, given the limited size of the dataset, the results obtained from this model may differ when applied to larger datasets. It should also be noted that the random forest model employed a random state value of 200, and altering this value may result in different outcomes. In addition to that, dataset of different individuals with different target variables name can also be trained in this model to check the speaker at the time of testing it.

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